

Propicroscytus mirificus (Girault)[Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae] correct name for the larval parasite of rice gall midge

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Obtusiclava oryzae Subba Rao is the most important larval parasite of rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood Mason) in India, Indonesia, and Thailand. It is also the type-species of the genus *Obtusiclava* Subba Rao, 1973 [ref: Subba Rao, B.R. 1973. Descriptions of a new species and genus of *Pteromalidae* (Hymenoptera) parasitic on *Pachydiplosis oryzae* (Wood-Mason) (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae). Bull. Ent.Res. 62:627-29].

In 1978, after examining Girault's types in Queensland Museum, Australia, Boucek discovered that the *Obtusiclava* is the same genus as *Propicroscytus Szelenyi*, 1941. Furthermore, *Propicroscytus mirificus* (Girault) has a new junior synonym in *O. oryzae* Subba Rao [ref: Boucek, Z. et al 1978. A preliminary review of *Pteromalidae* (Hymenoptera) of India and adjacent countries. Oriental Ins.12(4):433-67].

Henceforth, the genus *Propicroscytus* Szelenyi, 1941, having been described earlier, has priority over *Obtusiclava* Subba Rao, 1973. Therefore, the correct name for *O. oryzae* Subba Rao is *Propicroscytus mirificus* (Girault)

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